

Modelling and Simulation of Single-Phase Series APF Circuit by Using Control Strategy NLERE

(Pemodelan dan Simulasi Litar Sesiri APF Satu Fasa dengan Menggunakan Kawalan Strategi NLERE)

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ABSTRACT

In the minutes of life on earth, the application of power electronics equipment has been widely used in daily affairs such as lamps, computers, televisions and others. Indirectly, when a voltage source is supplied, it will produce a sine waveform while when a non-linear load is applied to a system it will produce a distorted current waveform which is known as a harmonic current. This causes a serious problem to the power distribution system due to the presence of harmonic voltage and current on the system. Non-linear loads are general terms for power electronics load such as rectifier circuits with inductive loads, adjustable speed drives (ASD), and so on. The issue of power quality is also a major concern in the power electronics industry due to the presence of harmonic currents that capable of reducing system efficiency and increasing power losses to the utilities. Therefore, harmonic current mitigation is the best solution to overcome the loss of power and efficiency as a result of the presence of harmonic current. There are various methods that can be taken to mitigate harmonic current, but for this study, a single phase series active power filter (SeAPF) circuit along with an estimation of non-linear load equivalent resistance (NLERE) control strategy in a way of computer modelling and simulation to mitigate harmonic current will be used. This method has also previously been implemented on a shunt active power filter circuit, therefore this study uses a series of active power filter circuit by using MATLAB Simulink software to perform simulation and modelling. The NLERE control strategy consists of three main strategies, namely the first strategy is by detecting and extracting current containing harmonic component, second, by performing a control system method to generate a compensated voltage indirectly will produce a control signal and the third strategy is by comparing the control signal with a carrier signal using a pulse width modulation (PWM) scheme to produce a gating signal. From the simulation, a total harmonic distortion (THD) and power factor (PF) can be measured and the resulting waveform can be identified and analyzed. The THD value for a model should be less than 5% according to IEEE 519 standard and the power factor value is closed to one. Finally, harmonic current successfully mitigated and compensated by using the proposed control strategy.

Keywords: Harmonic Current; SeAPF; Control Strategy; NLERE; THD

ABSTRAK

Dalam meniti kehidupan pada marcapada, penggunaan peralatan elektronik kuasa telah banyak digunakan di dalam urusan harian seperti lampu, komputer, televisyen dan sebagainya. Secara tidak langsung, apabila sumber voltan dibekalkan ia akan menghasilkan gelombang sinus manakala apabila beban tak lurus digunakan untuk sesuatu sistem ia akan menghasilkan gelombang yang terherot dimana ia dikenali sebagai arus harmonik. Hal ini menimbulkan permasalahan yang serius kepada sistem pengagihan kuasa disebabkan oleh kehadiran arus dan voltan harmonik pada sistem. Beban tak lurus adalah istilah umum bagi beban elektronik kuasa yang berkaitan dengan litar penerus dengan beban kearuhan, pemacu kelajuan laras (ASD), dan sebagainya. Isu kualiti kuasa juga menjadi perhatian utama dalam industri kuasa elektrik kerana kehadiran arus harmonik yang mampu untuk mengurangkan kecekapan sistem dan meningkatkan kehilangan kuasa kepada utiliti. Oleh yang demikian, pemampasan arus harmonik merupakan penyelesaian yang terbaik untuk mengatasi kehilangan kuasa dan kecekapan akibat daripada kehadiran arus harmonik. Terdapat pelbagai kaedah yang boleh diambil untuk memampas arus harmonik, akan tetapi untuk kajian ini akan menggunakan litar penuras kuasa aktif sesiri (SeAPF) satu fasa beserta dengan strategi kawalan penganggaran rintangan setara beban tak lurus (NLERE) secara pemodelan dan simulasi berkomputer untuk memampas arus harmonik. Kaedah ini juga sebelum ini pernah dilaksanakan menggunakan litar penuras kuasa aktif pirau, oleh itu kajian ini menggunakan litar penuras kuasa aktif sesiri dengan menggunakan perisian MATLAB Simulink untuk melakukan simulasi dan pemodelan. Strategi kawalan NLERE terdiri daripada tiga strategi utama iaitu yang pertama dengan mengesan dan mengeluarkan arus yang mengandungi komponen harmonik, yang kedua dengan melakukan sistem kawalan untuk menghasil voltan terpampas secara tidak langsung isyarat kawalan akan terhasil, dan strategi yang ketiga adalah dengan membandingkan isyarat kawalan dengan isyarat pembawa di dalam skema permodulatan lebar denyut (PWM) untuk menghasilkan isyarat get. Daripada simulasi, jumlah herotan harmonik (THD) dan faktor kuasa

(PF) dapat diukur dan bentuk gelombang yang terhasil dapat dikenalpasti dan dianalisis. Nilai THD untuk sesuatu pemodelan hendaklah kurang daripada 5% mengikut piawaian IEEE 519 dan nilai faktor kuasa adalah hampir kepada satu. Akhir sekali, arus harmonik berjaya dikurangkan dan dipampas dengan menggunakan strategi kawalan yang dicadangkan.

Kata Kunci: Arus Harmonik; SeAPF; Strategi Kawalan; NLERE; THD

INTRODUCTION

In this present era of modernity, the detection and understanding of harmonic is very important and should be studied, so that the presence of harmonic current, can be detected and the causes and ways of overcoming it can be strategized. Adversely, when a voltage source is supplied, a pure sine waveform is produced, as shown in Figure 1, while if a non-linear load is used for a system, a harmonic current distortion wave is produced as shown in Figure 2. In short, when a non-linear load is applied to a system, harmonic current is produced.

FIGURE 1. Sinusoidal source voltage, v_s

FIGURE 2. Distorted waveform of source current, i_s

In industry, power electronics equipment has a very high level of application. This will be a serious problem due to the presence of harmonic voltage in the power distribution system when electronics equipment is used. Each power electrical user is responsible for limiting the harmonic voltage resulting from the harmonic current from the consumer power electronics itself. In 1994, in Japan, guidelines for harmonic control were formulated and are now widely used to ensure that harmonic current is always maintained (Fujita, 1997). Ideally, in order to have the source current, i_s free from harmonic distortion, the harmonic component and reactive power can be mitigated by using an active power filter to allow only basic component to exist (Akagi & IEEE, 2005). Currently, deviation due to non-linear load applications have resulted in an increase in the total number of harmonic current and voltage in the alternating current (AC) system, especially in distribution system. The non-linear load produces harmonic and reactive power from the AC line, thereby reducing efficiency and power factors (Chattopadhyay et al., 2011). This non-linear load can be divided into two categories, namely

voltage and current source respectively, both used in conversion, transition, downstream power electrical arrangement, including manufacturing, commercial and residential installations.

Non-linear loads are apparently a cause of harmonic current distortion, which in some cases, can also distort the voltage waveform at the same time (Acha & Madrigal, 2001). Due to the existence of harmonic current, the use of non-linear load will also adversely affect the electrical system. Among the adverse effects on the system are such as overload current as well as overheating of components, transformers and electric generator (Watson & Arrillaga, 2003). In addition, it will result in power loss to the utility due to transfer of electrical energy to heat energy. On the consumer side, bill payment will be higher even though the level of electricity consumption and efficiency is getting lower. Therefore, harmonic current compensation is the best solution to overcome the damage caused by harmonic distortion and to reduce the losses that occur on electrical system. This action is very important to most utilities in the world including Tenaga Nasional Berhad (TNB) in Malaysia.

Harmonic Current

Harmonic current distortion can be suppressed by using an active power filter circuit (APF). Therefore, from such compensation, the total harmonic distortion (THD) value can be measured to find out the total of percentage after compensation. To determine the best THD value, the IEEE 519 standard has been used as a measure of the effectiveness of a system. According to the following standards, Table 1 summarizes the distortion limits for voltage and harmonic currents (Lam et al., 2014):

TABLE 1 Limits of Harmonic Current Distortion

Standards	THD Current (%)
IEEE 519:1992	20 (for small consumers)
	5 (for large consumers)
IEC 61000-3-2	16 (for loads smaller than 16 ^{kw})

Harmonic current distortion occurrence as a result of the connection of non-linear load and results in power loss to the utility. This is of great concern because it affects the power quality of electricity, abnormal heating of conductors, and devices, resulting in overload and even loss of power to feeders, power generators and transformers. There are several methods based on APF that can mitigate for harmonic current distortion such as the non-linear load equivalent resistance estimation strategy (NLERE).

The aforementioned method has previously been carried out using the shunt active power filter (SAPF) method but the series active power filter (SeAPF) method has never been implemented yet. A MATLAB Simulink software was chosen to carry out this research by modelling and simulating the circuit because it has all the necessary components and it is very simple to use.

To achieve the first objective which is to analyze the waveform of the harmonic current by using various types of non-linear loads. Indirectly, the first method taken is to simulate and model a variety of non-linear loads to find out the value of THD and the power factor based on the modeling. The variety of non-linear load models is such as the current source non-linear load model, R-L, voltage source non-linear load model, R-C, and diode rectifier circuit with R-L-C load.

Generally, this method is implemented by modeling the circuit using MATLAB Simulink tool. The simulation utilizes the parameters used for modeling non-linear load variation as shown in Table 2. This simulation also aims to identify the resulting waveform at the voltage source, v_s and current source, i_s as well as measure the amount of current total harmonic distortion (THD) produced before being mitigation by the SeAPF.

TABLE 2 Non-linear Load Diversity Circuit Parameters

Load Circuit	V_s (V)	f (Hz)	L_s (mH)	R_s (Ω)	R_o (Ω)	L_o (mH)	C_o (μ F)
R-L	230	50	1	0.2	10	20	-
R-C	230	50	1	0.2	10	-	330
R-L-C	230	50	1	0.2	20	30	2000

The non-linear load circuit model basically uses a voltage source that is connected to the non-linear load by diversifying on each load modeling i.e. current source linear load, RL, voltage source linear load, RC, and linear load with RLC load. The modeling of this load circuit can be seen by referring to Figures 3, 4, and 5 respectively:

FIGURE 3. Voltage source non-linear load model

FIGURE 4. Current source non-linear load model

FIGURE 5. Diode rectifier with R-L-C load

Power factor (PF) will also be calculated. The power factor is obtained by the actual power (P) divided the apparent power (S), which is the apparent power equal to the voltage source (in rms) multiplied by the current source (in rms). This can be expressed by the following mathematical formulas:

$$PF = \frac{P}{|S|} \tag{1}$$

$$S = V \times I \tag{2}$$

SeAPF Circuit Model

The series active power filter (SeAPF) circuit has been modelled to eliminate harmonic distortion. The objective of SeAPF control is to generate appropriate gating signals for switching

devices based on the estimation of compensation reference signals (Salam et al. 2006). The SeAPF circuit requires a transformer to inject a compensated voltage. It is located in between the voltage source and the non-linear load. It works as a harmonic isolator. The SeAPF also consists of an active component i.e. insulated gate bipolar transistor (IGBT) which acts as switching device. The APF section also consists of direct current (DC) to alternating current (AC) inverter where the capacitor will act as energy storage element. The SeAPF circuit model can be seen in Figure 6, where the load circuit will be changed using RL, RC and RLC non-linear loads.

FIGURE 6. Basic SeAPF schematic circuit

Control Strategy NLERE

There are three stages of control approaches will be used to complete the series active power filter circuit that namely a non-linear load equivalent resistance estimation (NLERE). These control strategies used are harmonic detection, control circuit system, and PWM switching scheme. Basically, the first control strategy is to detect and extract the load current which containing harmonic component. The second step is to generate a control strategy related to voltage harmonic control. Third, after the compensation voltage, control signal is established, and then it will be compared to the carrier signal to produce a PWM gate pulse. In Figure 7 shows a summarized block of the non-linear load equivalent resistance estimation (NLERE) control strategy.

FIGURE 7 NLERE control strategy block diagram

Harmonic Detection

The first NLERE strategy is to detect and extract the load current containing the harmonic component which in turn will be filtered to generate a reference current and later transfer into the control

circuit system for the next strategy. The respective \$v_s\$ and \$i_s\$ are sensed, and being used as the input of filtration tool. The filtration tool that will be used to isolate these harmonic component is a low pass filter (LPF). Generally, a low-pass filter (LPF) functions as a separator of the harmonic component and fundamental component from their source signal. The LPF only allows low-frequency signals to pass through the filter.

The sine reference current, \$I_{s,ref}\$ will be generated for this strategy using mathematical derivatives and filter components. Prior to be filtered, those input quantities are transformed into an absolute number respectively. After passing the LPF, the average value of output voltage, \$V_o\$ and output current, \$I_o\$ are developed. A non-linear load equivalent resistance, \$R_e\$ is produced by dividing voltage, \$v_s\$ to the output current, \$I_o\$. The calculation of the non-linear load equivalent resistance is given as follows:

$$R_e = \frac{V_o}{I_o} \tag{3}$$

Next, to obtain the sine reference current, \$I_{s,ref}\$, the \$v_s\$ divides the non-linear load equivalent resistance value. This can be defined by the equation below:

$$I_{s,ref} = \frac{V_s}{R_e} \tag{4}$$

A summary of this strategy is illustrated in Figure 8, where the production of sine reference current, \$I_{s,ref}\$ is generated from mathematical calculation.

FIGURE 8. \$I_{s,ref}\$ calculation block diagram

Control Circuit System

The second NLERE control strategy is to design a control circuit system aimed at producing the control signal, \$u\$ and the compensate voltage, \$V_c^*\$. The compensated voltage, \$V_c^*\$ is built from a harmonic current component that is a derivative of the reference voltage compensation. This compensated voltage is presented in the equation below:

$$V_c^* = K(I_{s,ref} - I_s) + V_L \tag{5}$$

where \$I_{s,ref}\$ subtracted the source current, \$I_s\$ prior to be multiplied by a constant, \$K\$ which represents a virtual resistance value. The block diagram for this calculation is depicted in Figure 9.

FIGURE 9. V_c^* calculation block diagram

PWM Switching Scheme

The third NLERE control strategy is generating the control signal, u resulting from the second strategy. It will be compared in the PWM switching scheme which produces the gating signal and then sends to the IGBT switches to operate. For the switching control scheme, the PWM bipolar (BPWM) technique has been selected and the output pulse trains are arranged sequentially, used to control the operation of opening and closing the insulated gate bipolar transistor (IGBT) devices. In this study, a switching control scheme was used to generate a gating signal, g with a frequency of 20 kHz. Next, the control signal, u will be compared to the carrier signal to produce a pulse. Thus, when the carrier signal is greater than the control signal it produces a pulse at 1 or high, while the carrier signal is lower than the control signal it will produce a pulse at 0 or low. The carrier signal frequency determines the switching frequency. Figure 10 depicts the basic PWM switching scheme applied.

FIGURE 10. PWM switching control scheme

SeAPF Circuit with NLERE Control Strategy

The complete modeling simulation for this study contains the SeAPF circuit along with the three non-linear load equivalent resistance estimation control strategies capable of compensating for harmonic current distortion. The circuit model also has a passive power filter (PPF) that is installed in between the transformer and the non-linear load. This passive component consists of the 3rd and 5th tuned L-C filters, where it is used to

suppress the specific harmonic current. The parameter used for the 3rd tuned L-C filter is that its inductance value is $L_{3rd} = 1$ mH while the capacitor value is $C_{3rd} = 1141$ μ F. On the other hand, the 5th tuned L-C filter has the inductance value of $L_{5th} = 1$ mH while the capacitor value is $C_{5th} = 409$ μ F. Figure 11 shows a block diagrams of compensation process carried out using the APF.

FIGURE 11. Basic control strategy of SeAPF

Harmonic current distortion compensation is carried out using SeAPF circuit with NLERE control strategy and subsequent measurement of total harmonic distortion (THD) has been taken using the simulation in MATLAB Simulink software. The THD is based on Fast Fourier transform (FFT) technique. THD value measurements were taken for each non-linear load model before and after the SeAPF circuit connection. Measurement of THD values and power factor (PF) was taken on each model of the SeAPF circuits to achieve the objectives of this study. Measurement and calculation for the PFs are taken using equation (1).

MATLAB Simulink Simulation

The MATLAB Simulink software simulation tool is used to model and simulate non-linear load equivalent resistance estimation control strategies for three different non-linear loads. These non-linear loads consists of the non-linear load current source model, R-L, voltage source model, R-C, and diode rectifier with R-L-C load. These models are illustrated in Figures 12. Before and after compensation results are performed using the proposed control strategy of SeAPF circuit. The parameters used for each simulation tests are listed in Table 3.

TABLE 3. Parameters of SeAPF circuit and the system

Litar Beban	V_s (V)	f (Hz)	L_s (mH)	R_s (Ω)	R_o (Ω)	L_o (mH)	C_o (μ F)	C_c (μ F)	L_c (mH)	C_{dc} (μ F)
R-L	230	50	1	0.2	10	20	-	0.33	1	3000
R-C	230	50	1	0.2	10	-	330	0.33	1	3000
R-L-C	230	50	1	0.2	20	30	2000	0.33	1	3000

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results of simulation for a variety of non-linear loads were taken by identifying their respective waveforms and measuring their total harmonic distortion (THD) alongside the power factor (PF) also.

Modelling of SeAPF Circuit with NLERE Control Strategy

Modeling and simulation results using SeAPF circuit together with complete NLERE

control strategy to compensate harmonic distortion of the source current have been obtained. Measurement of the total harmonic distortion (THD) has also been measured using the simulation tool available on MATLAB Simulink software which is based on FFT analysis. The power factor (PF) measurement is also implemented using the formula in equation (1). The complete SeAPF schematic circuit and the test system has been successfully designed and modeled as depicted in Figure 12.

FIGURE 12 A complete model SeAPF schematic circuit with the proposed NLERE control strategy

THD and PF Values

Based on the results for the total harmonic current distortion (THD) and the value of the power factor obtained for each non-linear loads of R-L, R-C and R-L-C is summarized in Table 4. The waveform shape of the non-linear load for before and after compensation can be referred in the following figures alongside with the THD and PF values.

FIGURE 13. I_s before compensation (R-L)

FIGURE 14. I_s after compensation (R-L)

FIGURE 15. I_s before compensation (R-C)

FIGURE 16. I_s after compensation (R-C)

FIGURE 17. I_s before compensation (R-L-C)

FIGURE 18. I_s after compensation (R-C)

TABLE 4. THD and PF values before and after compensation

Load Circuits	Total Harmonic Distortion, THD (%)		Power Factor, PF	
	Before Compensation	After Compensation	Before Compensation	After Compensation
RL	19.81	2.79	0.9504	0.9969
RC	56.57	7.56	0.9213	1.0000
RLC	35.53	2.73	0.8369	0.9149

The summary from Table 4, shows that for the non-linear loads of R-L and R-L-C, a change in THD value after the compensation successfully achieved a THD value of less than 5% which are 2.79% and 2.73% respectively. This is in accordance with the IEEE 519 standard that the value limit for total harmonic distortion (THD) must be less than 5%. However, for the R-C non-linear load has a THD value of 7.56% after compensation using the SeAPF circuit together with the NLERE control strategy, hence it has a THD value of more than 5%. However, this does not mean that the SeAPF circuit and the NLERE control strategy are ineffective in mitigating for harmonic currents, but for R-C load it requires additional control tuning and improving the circuit system design. In addition, the method used is also able to compensate harmonic current for R-C

non - linear loads which is the value of THD before mitigation is 56.57% to 7.56% after mitigation. This means that this method is valid and able to mitigate harmonic current for all tested non-linear loads.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the achievement of the objectives of this study has been successfully using the methods described before. The first objective is to analyze the harmonic current waveform using various types of non-linear loads that have been successfully produced and implemented. Modelling and simulation of various non-linear loads such as current source non-linear load, R-L, voltage source non-linear load, R-C and diode rectifier with R-L-C load. The factors are by identifying the resulting

waveform and measuring the total harmonic distortion (THD) and power factor (PF) before and after the compensation process is implemented for each non-linear load application.

The second objective has also been successfully developed, namely the development of non-linear equivalent resistance estimation (NLERE) control strategy using a series active power filter (SeAPF) circuit capable of mitigating harmonic current when a variety of non-linear loads are used. The control strategy produced has three main strategies namely the first harmonic current detection which aims to detect and remove load current containing harmonic distortion. The second NLERE strategy is to use a control system to produce a compensating voltage reference, indirectly the control signal, u will be generated. The third strategy is the PWM switching scheme where the control signal, u resulting from the second strategy will be compared to the carrier signal using the pulse width modulation (PWM) scheme.

The third objective is to obtain the total harmonic distortion (THD) for the source current will not exceeding 5% according to the standards set by IEE 519 and to correct the power factor close to unity that has been successfully computed and produced. This is because the complete modelling of a single-phase series active power filter together with the three strategies of NLERE has been modeled and simulated.

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